

Emotional Intelligence of Adolescents in Relation to Their Peer Pressure

Dr. Rohit Bhandari

Assistant Professors
Dev Samaj College of Education
Chandigarh

Dr. Madhavi Goyal

Assistant Professors
Dev Samaj College of Education
Chandigarh

Abstract:

The present research aims to examine the emotional intelligence of adolescents in relation to their peer pressure. The current study targeted a population of 200 adolescents of Chandigarh. Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) by Mangal and Mangal (2009) and Peer Pressure Scale (PP) by Singh and Saini (2010) have been used for research purpose. Descriptive survey was done for the collection of data. The data was analysed statistically by using mean, S.D., t-test and Pearson's coefficient of correlation. Findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the peer pressure of male and female students of secondary schools. Also, the study resulted that no significant interactional effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents was found and a significant correlation was found between emotional intelligence and peer pressure environment of adolescents. The study helps the teachers to understand various aspects or factors which affect emotional intelligence of the adolescents and suggested that the teacher can teach and counsel the students that how to manage their emotions and peer pressures and also motivate them to build positive relationships and study also recommended that schools can provide supportive school environment where students feel valued for their individuality can reduce the impact of negative peer pressure and promote positive social interactions.

KEY WORDS: *Emotional Intelligence and Peer Pressure*

INTRODUCTION

Emotions are the important aspects of life and adolescence period act as a transition stage from immature modes of life to development of maturity in physical, emotional, social and intellectual aspect of development. Today, adolescents are facing psychological problems such as depression, anxiety and frustration one of them increasing with rapid rate is aggression due to less emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence, once developed, can create the avenue for a productive, rewarding and fulfilling life (Yadav, 2014). Peer pressure is feeling pressure from other age mates to do something harmful for self and others. Peer pressure is when you are influenced by other people (your peers) to act in a certain way. Elias (2004) said that emotional intelligence is helping to focus on what it means to be complete human beings. These abilities allow an individual to recognize and regulate emotion, develop self-control, set goals, develop empathy, resolve conflicts and develop skills needed for leadership and effective group

participation. Wool fork, Hughes and Walkup (2008) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to process emotionally information accurately and efficiently. Craig et. al,(2013) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive emotions to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth. Sim and Koh (2003) defined peer pressure as any attempt by one or more peers to compel an individual to follow in the decisions or behaviours favoured by the pressuring individual or group. Singh and Saini(2010) defined peer pressure as a feeling pressure from age-mates to do something harmful for self and others.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Aggarwal and Bhalla (2014) examined the relationship between emotional intelligence of 150 senior secondary school adolescent in relation to their creativity. The results of the study showed that there is a significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and creativity. Suresh (2015) examined the correlation between emotional intelligence and job involvement of school teachers. Study was conducted on a sample of 100 teachers (47 male and 53 female) of Thajavur District, Tamil Nadu. The results indicated that the emotional intelligence of the teacher is high, job involvement is satisfactory and the correlation between emotional intelligence and job involvement is significant. Noor, Bader, Ali and Ra'ed (2019) examined relationship among emotional intelligence and job performance in Jordanian banks. Study was conducted on 447 valid returns. The results showed that both emotional intelligence and conflict management styles were significantly and positively related to job performance. The results also showed that emotional intelligence and conflict management styles were positively and significantly related to each other.

Thakur, Lakhani and Maniar (2020) conducted a study on a sample of 50 working people (25 females and 25 males) of organization of Mumbai and examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of working people. The study found that there is a strong relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. Trigueros et. al, (2020) analysed the relationship between emotional intelligence and social skills, and how these two variables influence bullying. In this study, 912 Spanish high school students, 471 boys and 441 girls aged 14–16 years, participated. The results of the study reflected that there was a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and social skills and a negative relationship with respect to bullying. In turn, social skills reflected a negative relationship with respect to bullying. Kim, Seon-Jeong; Lim, Young-Jin (2021) studied to find out relationships between peer pressure, social networking site (SNS) addiction, and SNS-use motives in Korean adolescents. Adolescent SNS users (N = 300, 52.70% female) completed self-report measures of peer pressure, SNS addiction, and SNS-use motives. Findings indicated that adolescents reporting more peer pressure had higher levels of SNS addiction. Moreover, the relationship between peer pressure and SNS addiction was mediated by coping and social-conformity use motives. Results are discussed in terms of implications for prevention and intervention, for adolescents facing peer pressure. Kaila and Cherian (2024) focused on the connections between

peer pressure, emotional intelligence (EI), and mental well-being in youthful grown-ups. The results of the study revealed that a significant negative correlation between peer pressure and mental well-being, indicated that higher peer pressure is associated with lower mental well-being. Conversely, a significant positive correlation is observed between emotional intelligence and mental well-being and suggested that greater emotional intelligence is linked to enhanced mental well-being. However, no significant correlation is found between peer pressure and emotional intelligence.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The study of emotional intelligence in relation to peer pressure is essential for understanding how adolescents cross complex social environments where peer pressure can influence behaviour, decisions, and identity. The review of related literature shows that very few studies have been carried out on emotional intelligence in relation to peer pressure. Emotional intelligence plays a critical role in struggling negative peer influences and making independent, value-driven decisions. In an age where peer pressure can manifest both in-person and online, individuals with higher emotional intelligence are better equipped to handle social stress, assert boundaries, and maintain mental well-being. Hence in the light of above discussion and seeing the importance of emotional intelligence and peer pressure, the investigator has planned to undertake the present study concerning the emotional intelligence of adolescents in relation to their peer pressure.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Emotional intelligence of adolescents in relation to their peer pressure

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study and compare the peer pressure of male and female adolescents.
2. To study the interactional effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents.
3. To find out correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant difference in the peer pressure of male and female adolescents.
2. There will be no significant interactional effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents.
3. There will be no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents.

DESIGN AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

For the present study, a descriptive survey was used as design of the study. The sample of the study consisted of 200 (100 Male and 100 Female) secondary students of Chandigarh, these students were selected randomly from a list of government and private schools through a lottery system. Equal numbers of students were taken as samples of the study.

TOOLS EMPLOYED FOR THE STUDY

The study employed following tools for the purpose of data collection:

- 1) Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) by Mangal and Mangal (2009)
- 2) Peer Pressure Scale (PP) by Singh and Saini (2010)

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

HYPOTHESIS 1

Hypothesis 1 states, “There will be no significant difference in the peer pressure of male and female adolescents.” This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 1 The pictorial form of this Table has been presented in Figure 1.

Table 1: Results showing mean, S.D. and t-ratio of peer pressure between male and female adolescents

Variable	M1 (Male=100)	M2 (Female=100)	S.D.1 (Male)	S.D.2 (Female)	t- value	Level of Significance
Peer Pressure	66.25	62.12	15.15	15.92	1.867	NS

Table 1 represents that the mean scores of peer pressure of male and female adolescents. The mean score of peer pressure of males was 66.25 and females was 62.12 Their respective standard deviation was 15.15 and 15.92. The t-ratio was found to be 1.86.

Discussion of Results

The calculated t-ratio is not significant, which indicates that male and female adolescents do not differ significantly in their peer pressure.

Hence, hypothesis 1, i.e., “There will be no significant difference in the peer pressure of male and female adolescents”, has been accepted.

HYPOTHESIS 2

Hypothesis 2 states, “There will be no significant interactional effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents.” This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 2.

Table 2: Main Interactional Effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents.

Summary of ANOVA						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	Level of Significance	
Among group	291557.36	1	291557.36	-	-	
Peer pressure	4452.42	56	79.50	1.868	Not Significant	
Gender	95.17	1	95.17	2.235	Not Significant	
Peer pressure*Gender	1786.91	27	66.18	1.555	Not Significant	
Within group	494228.00	197	-	-	-	
Total	11479.24	196	-	-	-	

Table 2 represents that the mean square of peer pressure (high and low) of adolescents was 79.50. The calculated F-value came out to be 1.868, which is not significant. The mean square of gender of adolescents was 95.17. The calculated F-value came out to be 2.235, which is not significant.

The mean square calculated for the interactional effect between peer pressure and gender of adolescents was 66.18 and F-value was 1.555, which is not significant.

Discussion of Results

The results show that adolescents partially differ in their emotional intelligence in relation to their gender and peer pressure. Hence, hypothesis 2, i.e., “There will be no significant interactional effect of peer pressure and gender on the emotional intelligence of adolescents”, has been accepted.

HYPOTHESIS 3

Hypothesis 3 states, “There will be no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents.” This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 3.

Table 3: Results showing correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents

Variable	Emotional Intelligence
Peer pressure	-0.188**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From Table 3, it can be seen that the coefficient of correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure came out to be -0.188, which is significant at 0.01 level of significance.

Discussion of Results

From the results, a positive significant correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents is found at 0.01 level of significance.

Hence, hypothesis 3, i.e., “There will be no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and peer pressure of adolescents”, has been rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study has been aimed to study the emotional intelligence of adolescents in relation to their peer pressure. But this study will go a long way as it would open new way for

educationists and policy maker to prepare a framework for emotional intelligences in the present scenario.

- The findings of the study help the teachers to understand various aspects or factors which affect emotional intelligence of the adolescents.
- The teacher can provide adequate and helpful environment to the students to make them emotionally strong and mature.
- The teacher can teach and counsel how to manage their emotions and peer pressures and also motivate them to build positive relationships.
- Schools can provide supportive school environment where students feel valued for their individuality can reduce the impact of negative peer pressure and promote positive social interactions.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

The present study was limited to the Chandigarh, union territory only. Such studies can also be varied out in Punjab and other parts of the country.

- The present study can be applied to large population.
- The present study can be conducted for any city also.
- It can be considered for varied categories of students. The school and university students can be covered up for further study.

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